

INHERITANCE AND VARIABILITY OF SOME MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS IN ECOLOGICALLY AND GEOGRAPHICALLY DISTANT G' OZA HYBRIDS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10052282>

Abstract : This in the article valuable economic features learning results given simple and complicated hybrids second generation medium fibrous cotton varieties different water under the circumstances . Learned productivity coefficients to the genotype dependence percent consists of of the sign legacy and the environment conditions .

Key Keywords : cotton , optimal background , simulation done water supply is complex hybrids , simple hybrids , heredity , variation ;

Our republic cotton farming industry only artificial to water based on Last _ in years 1 hectare in Spain and Israel on the field cotton Cultivation water consumption does _ In our country this indicator is 12 thousand meter organize is enough Here _ water calculated dams , irrigation _ systems and answer through entered water evaporates . Republic according to average common water 57,781 km of consumption organize reached 93% of them are rural farm crops in irrigation is used . Because of this from water efficient use great important important have _ Last in years climate change because of water deficiency surface came _ And this is _ _ in turn , yield has been harvest and his to quality negative effect does _ Water thrifty new technologies work exit necessary _ Village in the farm technology of types one to drought resistant varieties is to create . Goza _ varieties breeding as a result received of hybrids productivity comparative learning genetics and of selection main of duties is one The above in consideration received without of research purpose heredity and G in hybrids medium _ fibrous cotton varieties one of the plant productivity of the sign different different water supply variability in conditions (optimal and low) . Studies Uzbekistan _ Republic Sciences academy Experimental plants biology genetics Tashkent region of the institute Zangiota in the district is located territorial experience of the base experience in the field take went _

Materials and research methods . Har different come output cotton Varieties : Navbahor 2. Trust , AN 16, F hybrids of S 9081, S 9082 varieties . Studies different different water modes have in the backgrounds was conducted . Back in the background (experimental) cotton irrigation 1:1:0 scheme on 2 times held , of water common size , to water spent 3000 m/ gani organize did , in experience of cotton buds appear to be during one times and bloom Beginning during one times irrigation through simulation drought was created . Background 2 (control) plants vegetation during the 1:2:1 scheme 4 times according to irrigation done increased , for irrigation spent of water common volume is 5000 m/ ha organize did _

Research Results : One of the plant productivity of the sign variability volume according to cotton varieties optimal water groups with provide under the conditions of " Trust " grade 2 in " Navbahor" grade 6 , the remaining 3 and AN 16, S 9081, S 9082 varieties occupied _ 7th grade . One of cotton productivity in the circumstances variability identified. One plant for suitable coming optimal water supply 5 and 6 classes between Navbahor " 2 AN 16 and 6

classes in C grades , " Trust " and "S" grades and 5th grade it happened If this in the population one in the plant was 101.0-110.9 g plants studied if , then cotton raw material mass was 120.9 g plants only in 3 varieties note issued : Trust (3.3%), AN 16 (3.3%) and S. 9081 (13.3%). C 9081 and Confidence varieties for cotton of raw materials average weight high , i.e. 83.4 ± 2.5 , 84.1 ± 2.5 for 86.0 ± 2.5 g organize did _ Content change coefficient 11.3; 16.5 % out let _ That 's it shows that in varieties of the sign variability average was _ Everyone simple and complicated hybrids are positive in E and negative to transgression have has been one plant for suitable has been cotton productivity obvious manifestation it happened In normal F plants this of the sign heredity coefficient H from 0.45 to 0.64 being , this from the G plants of the trait to the F generation average and high level pass shows . Antonomov VA and Antonomov VA's are also authors with did in works (2010) [1], one spike N. cotton of mass productivity indicators suitable 0.47 0.75 and 0.32 0.67 respectively organize did _ In factories E of productivity 14 classes of variability organize did _ of plants big part combination (Navbahor 2 x İşış) x (AN 16 x S 9081), (Navbahor 2 x AN 16) x (İşışxS 9082) 81 090.9 g category (Navbahor 2 x S 9082) x (İşış x AN 16), (AN 16 9081) x (Navbahor 2 x Trust) class 91.0 100.9 g, combined (Trust S 9082) (Navbahor 2 x AN 16) class 61, 70.9 g and combined (Confidence x AN). 16) x (Navbahor 2 x C) class 80.9 g. These classes are modal classes as acceptance done _ So making , experiments to the results according to , big differences not observed . P generation simple and complicated hybrids between cotton of raw materials each one from the plant removable harvest by weight according to one plant 91.0 g for and from him more suitable will come That 's it shows that only complicated hybrids (AN 16 x C 9081) x (Navbahor 2 x Ishbar) productivity high has been genotypes in choosing high to productivity have will be complicated of hybrids some combinations simple hybrids from the combination superior to be can _ Complicated hybrids variability to the coefficient have _ This feature for V% in normal F plants like 38.8 % organize does and high to variability have _ Complicated plants between of the sign average indicator E combination (AN 16 x C 9081) x (Navbahor 2 x Trust) to advantage have is one _ plant for suitable was cotton yield 61.6 ± 2.2 g, other combinations from aesa 49 .5 increased _ From ± 1.5 g to 55.6 ± 1.8 g . Variability coefficient (V) indicators high , that is they are 35.2-42.8 % organize did _ And this that's it shows that it is complicated in plants productivity feature variability simple in plants such as big _ Received results that's it shows that in the circumstances birth feature heritage by doing in getting water supply , base number genotypic composition , that is of hybrids dependence .

References:

- 1.Autonomov and Goza smart and black root to decay endurance for intraspecific geographical Dissertation : Dissertation abstract . Diss. doc . Village farm Sci. Tashkent C.
- 2.Akhmedov Kha, Djumashev MMKrilova LG, Khokhlacheva VE Verticillium vita artificial in the background cotton in hybrids early cooking feature variability .
- 3.Kolesnih TI, Egorov VG Ontogeny during wheat classified water with provide plants by from water the most reasonable use for basis as . // Uzbekistan plant 1st congress of physiologists : Lecture theses . Tashkent.